

FORMATION OF A POSITIVE IMAGE OF THE STATE IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Annotation. At the center of the formation of the state image, diplomacy serves as an important factor in presenting the nation's historical values, policies and aspirations to the international community. In the article, the issues of forming a positive image of the state in the system of international relations were analyzed.

Key words: State image, diplomacy, socio-economic disparity, geopolitical conflicts and conflicts.

Introduction. Forming a positive image of the state in the system of international relations is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Media manipulation, conflicting interests, historical baggage, economic challenges, human rights records, geopolitical conflicts, and leadership transitions all contribute to the difficulty countries face in creating a favorable global perception. Addressing these challenges requires transparency, effective communication, and a commitment to ethical behavior.

Analysis and results. At the center of the formation of the state image, diplomacy serves as an important factor in presenting the nation's historical values, policies and aspirations to the international community. Diplomacy is the official activity of states in the field of foreign policy implementation, as well as protection of rights and interests abroad¹. Bilateral and multilateral engagements such as various talks and official summits provide platforms for countries to showcase their diplomatic prowess and commitment to global cooperation. Through these interactions, the countries gain experience in improving their image along with positive cooperation relations. In particular, "diplomatic efforts help to show the state as responsible, ready to engage in dialogue and resolve conflicts peacefully. Conversely, diplomatic mistakes or failures can damage a state's reputation and isolate it from the international community"².

It should be noted that historical events greatly contribute to the formation of the state's image. How a state portrays its history affects how it is

¹ Спёсий атамалар изоҳли луғати. -Т., 1996.

² Rachel G. The Hidden Curriculum: First Generation Students at Legacy Universities. Princeton, Nj, Jersi: Princeton University Press, 2021.

perceived and perceived by others. Positive or negative historical events shape collective memory and influence international relations. States may exaggerate the glorious periods of their history to enhance their image, or on the contrary try to downplay the less "favorable" aspects of their history. Furthermore, historical disputes and grievances can affect diplomatic relations and perpetuate negative perceptions, illustrating the complex relationship between history and state image.

One of the most important problems in the formation of the image of the state is the manipulation and the attempt to control the perception through the media. Today, the development of digital media and virtual networking platforms exacerbates this problem, as information can spread quickly, violently, and without proper context. States can fight against misinformation or biased information, which leads to a false image of their actions and intentions.

The formation of the state image becomes complicated due to the cultural differences between peoples and nations at different stages of history. Actions carried out by the state as a pragmatic necessity at a certain stage of history may be perceived as aggressive or destabilizing in another historical space and time. Different conflicts often arise from historical context, cultural norms, and social differences and differences. These differences can lead to unintended conflicts and damage the country's image on the world stage. For example, colonial legacies and historical baggage can undermine efforts to create a positive image of a particular nation. Past realities such as imperialism, exploitative policies, or the restriction of human freedoms have a negative impact on image-building qualities as they damage the state's image. "Attempts to distance themselves from these historical mistakes may be met with skepticism and opposition from other nations, hindering efforts to present a more positive image."³

Socio-economic disparity and problems in the country's internal development also affect its global image, of course. Examples include population poverty, inequality, and other factors. Countries struggling with violations of social justice principles and lack of critical infrastructure have difficulty projecting an image of stability, progress, and legitimacy. International relations actors often question the effectiveness of a government that cannot adequately address its domestic problems, which affects its potential to participate constructively on the global stage.

Conclusion. A country's human rights and moral behavior play a decisive role in shaping its image. Countries with questionable records on issues such as

³ Must-Okar, Ellen (2004) "Siyosiy muxolifatni boshqarish va manipulyatsiyasi", Qiyosiy siyosat , 36 (2) , 159-179-b.

civil liberties, freedom of expression, and treatment of minority groups may face criticism and condemnation from the international community. Such historical trends can overshadow any positive state initiatives, leading to reputational damage and limited diplomatic effectiveness.

Geopolitical conflicts and disagreements have a significant impact on how a nation is perceived by others. Adapting to contested social systems or intervening in conflicts can lead to threats from this association, even when a state's goals do not fully align with those of its allies. Maintaining a balance between maintaining alliances and upholding one's own values is a complex historical process, and it is a factor affecting the status of the state's image in the international arena.

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